

A.C.T.I.V.E. - ADVANCED CYBERNETIC TECHNOLOGY FOR INTERVENTION, VERSATILITY, AND EXPLORATION

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ANNOTATION

The aim of the study was to create an autonomous robotic platform capable of self-orientation and precise movement in real time. Such a platform is designed to operate in conditions dangerous to humans, which makes production safer and more efficient. The hypothesis was that combining computer vision with a smooth navigation system on Bezier curves would produce an inexpensive but highly accurate rover capable of confidently maneuvering in difficult industrial and rugged environments.

The work on the project included an analysis of existing localization methods, the development of a mechanical part using computer simulations, and then the creation and debugging of a prototype with its own navigation and visual software. The experimental part was based on engineering optimization: chassis rigidity was increased due to FEA analysis, and the rocker-bogie suspension provided high cross-country capability. Navigation is implemented using the Bezier curve algorithm, which forms smooth trajectories and allows you to avoid obstacles in dynamics.

The novelty of the project manifested itself in the modular design and the introduction of a unique Local Pathing algorithm. The development covers the entire cycle – from mechanics to autonomous software management, which emphasizes the high level of independence of work.

As a result, a prototype was created that successfully passed the tests. It demonstrated stable route construction, accurate obstacle avoidance, and the ability to escort objects. The increased rigidity of the chassis played a key role in the accuracy of the work. The practical value of the project is evident in the field of industrial safety, logistics automation, scientific research and even in the development of space technologies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Occupational injuries remain a key factor driving the need for automation of intra-warehouse and intra-plant logistics. According to the ILO, millions of accidents, including fatalities, are recorded annually, while national statistics in developed countries consistently record millions of non-fatal injuries [1][2]. In this context, the problem of localizing robotic platforms has become more pressing than ever. Localization is understood as the calculation of the robot's position and orientation in real time relative to elements around it and the work area. The accuracy of this assessment determines the safety of movement, adherence to process routes, and the throughput of material flows.

To address these issues, it was decided to develop this project. The main goal of the project is to create an autonomous robotic platform for industrial use capable of localization and navigation in real time without human intervention. This platform must be capable of movement along a predetermined trajectory, obstacle avoidance, object recognition, and the performance of manipulation operations in conditions potentially hazardous to human health and life. Additionally, the project aims to develop and test intelligent navigation algorithms that can be used in future research to increase the autonomy and versatility of mobile robots.

1.1 Scientific Novelty

1. Integration of a modular design, allowing for the rapid replacement of functional units;
2. Use of a local navigation algorithm based on Bézier curves, ensuring smooth and precise movement with minimal computational resources;
3. Implementation of a four-axis manipulator, which expands the rover's functionality, transforming it from a transport platform into a fully-fledged assistant for complex operations.

1.2 Practical significance

The rover can be used in a wide range of fields. In industrial safety, it reduces the need for human presence in hazardous conditions: mines, chemical plants, radioactive zones, fires, and rock falls. In science, the platform is useful for obtaining data in hard-to-reach areas such as deserts, volcanic regions, and the Arctic. The developed navigation and localization methods are also important for space: on the Moon and Mars, where GPS is unavailable and resources are limited, these technologies allow robots to operate autonomously. The design is modular and easily adapted to various tasks, such as cargo transportation.

1.3 Hypothesis

By combining computer vision methods with a smooth vector navigation system based on Bézier curves, we can create an autonomous rover that combines low sensor cost with high accuracy and safety.

1.4 Objectives

1. Study the main localization methods in production.
2. Create a CAD model of the robot from scratch and develop a new localization system.
3. Implement the robotic system.
4. Test the entire system.
5. Improve the rover and add new features.

2 RESEARCH PART

The following stages were completed during the work:

1. Literature review.
2. Selection and justification of localization methods.
3. Creation of a CAD model of the robot and design of the localization system.
4. Implementation of the prototype.
5. Testing and debugging the prototype.

Two principal approaches to robot spatial localization have emerged worldwide. The first method utilizes LiDAR. LiDAR measures distances to objects via laser pulses and generates a point cloud, which serves as the basis for map construction and pose estimation [3][6][7]. Nevertheless, the overall costs remain substantial. These encompass the sensor's price, mechanical integration expenses, power and networking requirements, plus regular calibration and maintenance [4]. In dusty, foggy, or aerosol-laden environments, measurement quality may deteriorate due to scattering and multipath reflections, compromising distance estimation reliability [5]. Moreover, high-density point clouds impose significant computational overhead during frame alignment, dynamic scene filtering, and maintenance of consistent local and global maps [3][7]. When scaling fleets of autonomous carts and robots, the total cost of ownership rises substantially, becoming the decisive factor in localization architecture selection [4].

The second method employs computer vision techniques. Mono and stereo cameras serve as data sources, which when combined with inertial measurements (IMU) enable the implementation of visual odometry and visual SLAM. This approach's appeal stems from the sensors' affordability and the wealth of visual information they provide. Cameras capture not only geometric data but also object shape features, proving particularly useful in human-machine environments featuring people, floor markings, cargo labels, and transport units [4][7]. Nevertheless, several limitations exist. The quality of motion estimation and mapping depends on lighting, contrast, and the presence of stable features. In dynamic environments with many people and carts, false matches increase, requiring dynamic masking and robust map update procedures [7][8]. Maintaining real-time operation often necessitates hardware acceleration, leading to increased computational costs, as well as the need for software model maintenance and regular parameter adjustments when transferring solutions between objects with different lighting and texture conditions [5][8].

Comparing two types of solutions in a typical warehouse and shop floor environment boils down to analyzing the trade-off between metric stability and ownership economics. LiDAR provides lighting independence and predictable geometry but increases capital and operational expenses while demanding protection and maintenance [3][4][5]. Visual odometry and visual SLAM reduce upfront costs through inexpensive sensors and add semantic context, yet shift expenses to the computational platform and remain dependent on lighting conditions [7][8]. One approach to resolving these challenges is the emerging trend toward hybrid architectures where LiDAR and camera channels are combined to enhance resilience against map changes and dynamic objects [7]. However, the ultimate selection criterion remains economic. Evaluation isn't based on individual sensor pricing but rather the total cost of ownership across a device

fleet, factoring in integration, computational infrastructure, service protocols, and safety requirements [4][7]. For industrial logistics, it's advisable to design localization systems around specific scenes, accuracy needs, and target safety metrics—methodically comparing LiDAR and computer vision options against aggregate costs and risks.

3 PROJECT EVOLUTION

Solution is an autonomous industrial rover with a Local Pathing system—a navigation framework engineered for unprecedented safety, precision, and robotic movement efficiency. Unlike traditional visual feature-based systems where trajectories are adjusted through jerky, abrupt turns, Local Pathing redefines autonomy with smooth, vector-based Bézier paths featuring continuous tracking.

When using camera perception, the rover recognizes objects, computes safe approach trajectories via Local Pathing, and autonomously manipulates them using a 4-axis robotic arm.

3.1 Version 1.0

The goal was to build a running prototype to understand the platform's limitations. The platform supported a robotic arm but lacked odometry and autonomy; driving was unstable; the arm and chassis mechanics were very weak. This prompted a complete redesign of the running gear and a transition to autonomy in the next iteration.

Fig. 0.0: Version 1.0 Prototype

3.2 Version 2.0 — "Rocker-Bogie + 4WS" and the first experiments with localization

A rocker-bogie suspension was developed to ensure all-wheel contact and off-road capability. Wheel steering servos were installed, effectively creating a four-wheel steering system (4WS).

The robot followed AprilTag beacons from the camera, but without odometry: it maintained its course solely by visual cues, resulting in sluggish movement between cues and instability when visibility was lost. Furthermore, the printed plastic hub/control arm mounts failed; camber appeared, and the wheel geometry shifted, further disrupting its course.

Fig. 0.1: Version 2.0 Details

4 APPLICATION OF GENERATIVE DESIGN AND FSAE ANALYSIS

During the design of the new version, a problem with wheel mounting was identified, stemming from an unsuccessful experience with the previous version. It was decided to use a bracket that connects the motor-wheel to a 20-series aluminum profile and functions as a short cantilever with an eccentric load.

The target criteria were set as follows: a minimum safety factor $K_{safety} \geq 2$ and a maximum deflection $\delta_{max} < 1$ mm.

The selected material was 3D-printed PETG, modeled as a linear-elastic isotropic material with the following properties: $E \approx 1.5$ GPa, $\nu \approx 0.38$, and $\rho \approx 1.14$ g/cm³. The model was created in Autodesk Fusion 360.

The applied load was defined as a force of $F = 100$ N, acting downward along the Z-axis on the support surface.

Fig. 0a. Initial geometry (v1): a bent plate with a long overhang.

Fig. 0b. Final geometry (v2): a V-shaped box-frame structure with a cross brace.

The longer the arm between the point of application of the force and the support, the greater the bending moment. With a thin cross-section, the stiffness is low, so the deflection is noticeable. Printed polymers are more sensitive to bending due to the anisotropy of the layers, so in v1, critical zones occur at the "root" of the cantilever. Therefore, the goal was to move from a "bending blade" to a "triangle-braced structure," where the elements operate in tension/compression.

4.1 Finite element analysis

The goal of finite element analysis (FEA) is to understand in advance, before printing or full-scale testing, where a part is overloaded and at risk of failure. The geometry is broken down into many small

finite elements, and stress-strain equations are solved for each. On the stress map, red zones indicate potentially hazardous areas, while blue zones indicate safe areas.

The analysis is based on standard formulas of continuum mechanics, the key formula being the von Mises stress:

$$\sigma_{vm} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}[(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)^2 + (\sigma_y - \sigma_z)^2 + (\sigma_z - \sigma_x)^2] + 3(\tau_{xy}^2 + \tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{zx}^2)}$$

FEA Stress Visualization

where $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$ are the normal stresses along the axes, and $\tau_{xy}, \tau_{yz}, \tau_{zx}$ are the shear stresses. The resulting scalar value σ_{vm} is compared with the material's yield strength, which is interpreted as the safety factor.

Before the simulation, the safety factor is defined as $K_{safety} = \sigma_t / \sigma_{vm}$ (for PETG, $\sigma_t \approx 23$ MPa). The higher the factor, the further the material is from yielding; a stable safety margin is considered to be $K_{safety} \geq 2$.

What the calculation of the original version (v1) showed

Fig. 1. v1: stress map (Max = 71.7 MPa), with the maximum located at the cantilever root.

Fig. 2. v1: displacement map (Max = 37.1 mm), indicating large deflection.

Fig. 3. v1: safety factor map (Min = 0.321), values below 1 are unacceptable.

A long lever increases the moment at the base; sharp internal corners concentrate stress. Printed plastic is particularly vulnerable to bending, resulting in a high stress peak, large deflection, and $K < 1$. The part will begin to flow under the operating load.

4.2 New geometry

The engineering goal is always to reduce flexural stiffness at a fixed mass and dimensions and to eliminate stress. Generative Design in Fusion 360 was used for form finding.

The idea of the algorithm: The compliance objective function $J = F^T u$ is optimized under a volume constraint $V \leq V_{max}$ and material-related technological constraints. Exploring different topologies redirects the load paths from a single cantilever to a triangular load-bearing scheme with closed force loops. As a result, the v2 geometry was obtained: a V-shaped frame with a central cross brace, large fillets, and cutouts in neutral stress regions.

In other words, the lever arm was shortened, meaning the elements now work primarily in tension/-compression rather than bending. This leads to small deflections and the elimination of peak stresses at the base.

Fig. 0c. V-shaped frame structure (v2)

Checking the new version (v2):

Fig. 4 (v2)

Fig. 5 (v2)

Fig. 6 (v2)

Fig. 4. v2: von Mises stress map σ_{vm} (Max = 8.68 MPa), localized near the base.

Fig. 5. v2: safety factor map (Min = 2.651), above the target threshold.

Fig. 6. v2: displacement map (Max = 0.466 mm), deflection below 0.5 mm.

“Before/after” comparison under identical boundary conditions and a load of $F = 100$ N.

Metric	v1 (before)	v2 (after)	Change
$\sigma_{vm,max}$, MPa	71.7	8.68	↓ -88%
δ_{max} , mm	37.085	0.466	↓ -98.7%
$K_{safety,min}$	0.321	2.651	↑ ×8.3
ε_{max}	0.08	0.01	↓ -87%

Table 1: Comparison of FEA Results

An almost hundredfold reduction in deflection is the main indicator that the force path has shortened and the geometry has begun to work.

Production Notes (FDM):

Printing parameters of the parts:

- Layer orientation along the load path reduces interlayer shear and increases the effective stiffness.
- Four perimeters create a load-bearing shell, with 40–60% infill.
- Large internal radii and the absence of sharp edges reduce von Mises stress peaks at bends.

Results: FEA revealed where and why v1 failed. GD generated a geometry that shifts the load from bending to tension/compression; a follow-up simulation confirmed the design criteria: $K_{safety,min} \approx 2.65$,

$\delta_{max} \approx 0.466$ mm. Now, under $F = 100$ N, the part bends approximately 80 times less, and the safety factor has increased more than eightfold.

5 LOCAL PATHING

Effective autonomous navigation requires trajectories that not only bring the robot to the desired point, but also do so quickly, smoothly, and safely. Our Local Pathing (LP) solution utilizes a methodology based on Bézier curves. These curves allow trajectories to be described as polynomial functions of time and provide continuous coordinate values and their derivatives. Furthermore, LP combines feedback control (PIDF control), centripetal acceleration correction, and inertia compensation, ensuring smooth operation and robustness to external disturbances.

Key features include the following: fast trajectory execution, as control forces are calculated vectorially, and disturbance correction thanks to localization, which knows the robot’s current position at any given moment.

5.1 Mathematical foundations of Bézier curves

A Bézier curve is a parametric polynomial curve fully defined by a set of control points. For trajectory planning, cubic curves are the most convenient, which have four control points P_0, P_1, P_2, P_3 . The current coordinates of a point on the curve are given by a parameter $t \in [0, 1]$ and calculated as:

$$B(t) = (1-t)^3 P_0 + 3(1-t)^2 t P_1 + 3(1-t)t^2 P_2 + t^3 P_3.$$

At $t = 0$, the point is at P_0 , and at $t = 1$, it is at P_3 . The intermediate control points P_1 and P_2 define the shape of the trajectory, so moving them changes the curve’s slope or allows it to avoid obstacles. It is important to note that the curve is not parameterized by arc length: $t = 0.5$ usually does not correspond to half the path length, since a conversion between t and the percentage of the path traveled is used.

To compute the movement direction, the derivative of the curve with respect to the parameter is needed:

$$B'(t) = 3(1-t)^2(P_1 - P_0) + 6(1-t)t(P_2 - P_1) + 3t^2(P_3 - P_2).$$

The tangential angle (current heading) is determined as

$$\theta(t) = \text{atan2}(B'_y(t), B'_x(t)).$$

Normalizing the vector $B'(t)$ gives a unit tangent vector indicating the direction of motion.

Weierstrass’s theorem and the choice of the number of control points

According to the Weierstrass approximation theorem, any continuous curve on the interval $[0,1]$ can be approximated by a Bézier curve with a given accuracy. However, in practice, increasing the number of control points degrades controllability, as the complex shape can lead to sharp bends that the algorithm cannot track. Therefore, when constructing trajectories, it is recommended to limit the trajectory to a single segment of a 4-point curve between two robot poses, and only when necessary is a long trajectory broken into several links that are connected into a chain.

Trajectory generation

When planning a path, we choose the initial pose $P_0 = (x_0, y_0, \theta_0)$ and the final pose $P_3 = (x_f, y_f, \theta_f)$. The intermediate control points P_1 and P_2 are positioned to form the desired curvature radius. For example, P_1 can be placed at a distance d in the direction of the initial heading θ_0 , and P_2 at a distance d in the direction of the final heading θ_f . This ensures smooth entry and exit to the trajectory.

During autonomous operation, the robot can generate curves “on the fly,” using its current pose as P_0 and the goal pose as P_3 . Such lazy generation is supported by the API: `new BC(follower::getPose, new Pose(x, y))`.

Once the curve $B(t)$ is obtained, the algorithm discretizes the parameter t with step Δt and creates a table of points containing coordinates, orientation, and curvature $\kappa(t)$, computed as:

$$\kappa(t) = \frac{B'_x(t)B''_y(t) - B'_y(t)B''_x(t)}{(B'_x(t)^2 + B'_y(t)^2)^{3/2}}$$

where $B''(t)$ is the second derivative of the curve. Curvature is used to estimate centripetal acceleration and limit speed on sharp turns.

5.2 Target Speed and Braking Calculation

To stop precisely at the end of the curve, the robot must reduce speed as it approaches the goal. In LP, the kinematic equation is used:

$$v_t = \sqrt{-2a_t s},$$

where v_t is the target linear speed, $a_t < 0$ is the desired deceleration, and s is the remaining path length. The algorithm computes the target speed to ensure an accurate stop at the end of the path.

In addition, inertia must be considered: the robot continues moving even after power is removed. To account for this, the speed it would reach at the end of the path without power is first estimated:

$$v_f = \sqrt{v_i^2 + 2as},$$

where v_i is the current speed, a is the natural deceleration (measured experimentally), and s is the remaining distance. Then the speed reduction magnitude is computed:

$$p_d = v_i - v_f,$$

and the final target speed is decreased accordingly: $v_t = v_t - p_d$.

This adjustment allows predicting the effect of inertia and reducing power in advance, ensuring smooth stopping without overshoot.

Speed Controller: PIDF

Maintaining the target speed is handled by a PIDF controller (Proportional-Integral-Derivative with Feedforward), where: The P component corrects the error: $u_P = k_P \cdot e$, with e being the difference between target and actual speeds. The I component eliminates residual error by integrating over time. The D component reacts to the rate of change of the error. The Feedforward (F) predicts the power required to reach the target speed: $u_F = k_F \cdot v_t$.

The P and F components are primary: during steady-speed motion, F provides most of the power, and P corrects small deviations. However, during braking, the increased p_d requires reducing power more aggressively than proportional correction alone.

Orientation Control and Heading Interpolation

In addition to linear speed, the robot must maintain the correct heading. In practice, we use tangent orientation, meaning the robot always faces the tangent of the Bézier curve, which is automatically defined by the curve derivative.

The algorithm calculates the angular error $\Delta\theta = \theta_{target} - \theta_{current}$ and applies a separate PIDF controller for turning. In the simplest case, angular velocity ω is proportional to $\Delta\theta$, but integral or derivative terms can be added to reduce residual oscillations. The resulting control vector combines components for motion along the curve and rotational torque for turning the robot body.

Converting Linear Velocities to Wheel Speeds

Robots with different wheel types require different speed transformations. For example, a mecanum drive (four wheels mounted at 45°) uses:

$$\begin{aligned} v_{front-left} &= v_y + v_x + k\omega \\ v_{front-right} &= v_y - v_x - k\omega \\ v_{back-left} &= v_y - v_x + k\omega \\ v_{back-right} &= v_y + v_x - k\omega \end{aligned}$$

where k depends on the frame geometry (distance from the center of mass to the wheels).

Centripetal Acceleration Consideration

On turns, the robot experiences centripetal acceleration $a_c = v^2\kappa$. If it is too high, wheels may slip. LP limits speed based on the current curvature by specifying a maximum allowed a_c^{max} and computing the limit speed:

$$v_{max}(t) = \sqrt{\frac{a_c^{max}}{|\kappa(t)|}}.$$

The actual speed v_t is chosen as the minimum of the speed calculated from braking and the curvature limit, ensuring smooth trajectory following without wheel slip.

Appendix A: Simplified Java Example A simplified Java example demonstrates the LP algorithm, independent of specific libraries. It shows the core ideas: curve generation, tangent computation, PIDF control of linear and angular speeds, and conversion to wheel velocities. Only key methods are included.

Updated Algorithm Integration The hardware configuration remains unchanged: the 3rd-generation rover uses a rocket-bogie chassis, four driven wheels, and encoders for localization. Integration of the LPPathTracker algorithm is as follows:

Initialization: In `init()`, create an object managing trajectories, e.g., `RouteNavigator`. This class handles localization, sequence of curves, and motor commands. Initialize sensors and controllers, define Bézier curves for routes, and chain curves using `curveBuilder().addCurve(...).setOrientationInterpolation(...)` returning a `CurveChain` object describing the full sequence.

Update: In the main loop of autonomous or teleoperation mode, call `routeNavigator.refresh()`. This method reads the robot's current pose, selects the active curve segment, calculates target linear and angular speeds, and sends them to the drive system. In manual mode, automatic trajectory following can be activated via `routeNavigator.executeRoute(curveChain)` on button press.

Completion: Once the trajectory is finished, `routeNavigator.isRunning()` returns false. At this point, control can revert to manual mode, or a new curve can be generated and executed. This approach allows continuous path creation and traversal without stopping the main program.

6 DETECTION AND TRACKING OF OBJECTS

In addition to localization, the robot needed to be able to detect, estimate distance, and reliably follow a selected object. Version 3.0 of our robot added this capability, as the RGB camera captures an object (e.g., a cube) and estimates its position in the frame.

If the object moves, the robot adjusts its speed and direction, maintaining a small distance. This capability is in demand in robotic systems for logistics, service robotics, and training. This section outlines the mathematical foundations of the algorithm, provides an example implementation in Java, and describes how it integrates into the system.

Color Detection Using HSV

Standard cameras return images in BGR/RGB format, but for isolating a specific color, it is better to use the HSV model. In the hue–saturation–value color space, hue, saturation, and brightness (value) can be adjusted separately. Conversion from BGR to HSV is performed using `cv2.cvtColor`, and limits are applied with `cv2.inRange()`:

```
# Convert frame to HSV
hsv_img = cv2.cvtColor(frame, cv2.COLOR_BGR2HSV)
# Threshold by color: keep pixels within the specified range
mask = cv2.inRange(hsv_img, lower_hsv, upper_hsv)
```

Contour Detection and Measurement in Pixels

On the binary mask, contours are found using `cv2.findContours()`, and the contour with the largest area is selected. Then, a minimum bounding rectangle is computed with `cv2.boundingRect()`, approximating the object's projection on the image. From this rectangle, we extract:

- Width of the object in pixels P (horizontal dimension of the rectangle)
- Height H and center position (x_c, y_c)
- Contour area

The width in pixels is treated as the perceptual width, which is needed for distance estimation. The rectangle's center is used to calculate the angular offset relative to the frame center.

Distance Estimation to the Object

Distance is estimated using camera geometry. Let the object have a known physical width W (e.g., a calibrated cube), and let its projection in the frame be P pixels. How are W , P , and distance D related?

Using trigonometry, if the camera has a horizontal field of view θ , then the angle subtended by the object is

$$\text{angle} = \theta \cdot \frac{P}{S},$$

where S is the frame width in pixels. By similar triangles, the distance is:

$$D = \frac{W}{2 \tan(\frac{\theta P}{2S})}.$$

In OpenCV frameworks, this is often expressed as:

$$\text{Angle of arc} = (\text{field of view}) \cdot \frac{P}{S}, \quad \tan(\text{arc}/2) = \frac{W/2}{D}.$$

In practice, it is often more convenient to use the focal length in pixels F . This can be obtained in advance by photographing an object of known width W_0 at a known distance D_0 :

$$F = \frac{P_0 D_0}{W_0}.$$

Then, for any new projection P , the distance estimate simplifies to:

$$D = \frac{WF}{P}.$$

Fig. 0.v

This ratio is widely used in robotics and is mentioned, for example, in computer vision forums. In our experiments, we calibrated the camera this way.

Distance to the Frame Center

In addition to radial distance, it is necessary to determine the angular displacement of the object relative to the camera axis. If the frame center has coordinate x_0 and the frame width is S , the displacement $\Delta x = x_c - x_0$ is proportional to the angle:

$$\phi = \frac{\theta}{S} \cdot \Delta x.$$

Knowing ϕ and the distance D , these values can be converted to a local target (e.g., world offset) and sent to the control system.

Contour-Based Control

A classical PIDF controller is used for smooth approach to the object. One control loop manages longitudinal speed (forward/backward motion), and the second controls angular speed (turning).

- The first controller input is the distance error: $e_D = D_{target} - D$
- The second controller input is the angular error: $e_\phi = -\phi$ (negative sign to turn toward the object)

The outputs are the target linear and angular velocities v and ω , which are limited to the chassis' maximum allowable values.

The longitudinal speed is also constrained by the trajectory curvature to prevent overly sharp turns. As shown in the Local Pathing methodology, the speed can be limited based on curvature:

$$v \leq \sqrt{\frac{a_c}{\kappa}},$$

where a_c is the maximum centripetal acceleration, and κ is the curvature.

Java Implementation Example

Appendix B provides a simplified example of the `VisionObjectTracker` class. It implements color-based detection, distance estimation, and command calculation for a mecanum chassis.

Key processing steps include: 1. Conversion to HSV 2. Color thresholding 3. Noise removal 4. Contour detection 5. Distance calculation

The `mecanumKinematics` function converts desired velocities into wheel powers for four wheels.

Integration into the Robot System

A single camera is rigidly mounted on the frame. In version 2.0, the platform used plastic brackets and lacked encoders, resulting in low accuracy and unstable construction. In version 3.0, reinforced brackets and wheel encoders were installed, and encoder data is combined with the camera using a Kalman filter to obtain a continuous pose estimate. Focal length in pixels is calibrated once.

Software Integration

The system consists of three modules: 1. **VisionModule** – processes frames and outputs distance and angular displacement. Uses the `VisionObjectTracker` class. 2. **NavigationModule** – handles localization (fusing camera and encoder data) and trajectory generation. 3. **DriveModule** – receives target speeds and controls the motors.

Algorithm workflow:

- **Initialization:** In `init()`, create `VisionObjectTracker`, `NavigationModule`, and PID controllers. Set target curves for movement (if combined with Local Pathing) or only distance-holding parameters. Input calibration values for F and HSV thresholds.
- **Update Loop:** Each frame, the camera sends an image to the `VisionModule`. The `update()` method returns distance and angle. Simultaneously, the `NavigationModule` updates the robot pose. Measured D and ϕ are sent to PID controllers, which compute linear and angular velocities. The drive module converts these into wheel speeds. If trajectory navigation (Local Pathing) is enabled, modules combine control: when an object is detected, tracking takes priority; otherwise, trajectory following continues.
- **Completion:** When the object is lost or the robot reaches the goal, the system either returns to normal navigation or stops movement. All PID controller errors and integrals are reset when switching modes.

CONCLUSION

In this project, we consistently addressed three key issues—trajectories, perception, and robustness—and refined them into a working system.

First, the motor-wheel bracket assembly was redesigned. FEA identified flaws in the basic shape (high stresses and deflection), and generative design suggested a V-shaped load-bearing system with short, closed load paths. Repeated simulations showed a reduction in maximum stress by approximately an order of magnitude, a decrease in deflection by almost a hundredfold, and an increase in the minimum safety factor to the required level. This eliminated mechanical error and stabilized the kinematics.

Second, the Local Pathing algorithm replaced the jerky motion between waypoints with continuous following of Bézier curves with pose correction. The robot traces a smooth trajectory, limits the speed based on curvature and natural braking, and then translates the target linear and angular velocities into actuator commands. As a result, we achieved predictable dynamics, no sharp turns, and stable path keeping even under external disturbances. This directly improves safety and repeatability of missions.

Thirdly, the OpenCV-based computer vision module gave the robot vision and simple scene understanding. Color/marker segmentation, morphology mask cleaning, and pinhole distance estimation (actual size, focus, pixel size) allow us to determine the cube's position in the frame and close the tracking loop: longitudinal error is controlled by a PID controller, and lateral displacement by chassis rotation. In practice, the robot reliably approaches an object and follows it as it moves away, without losing course stability. This module is critical for autonomous approach, pickup, and takeaway missions. The combined effect of three solutions—smooth trajectories, computer vision-based navigation, and rigid mechanics—transformed the platform from a prototype into a viable engineering model: autonomous approach to cargo, operator support at a safe distance, and operation in risk zones without human intervention. This reduces injuries, increases throughput, standardizes operational quality, and provides the basis for scaling the fleet of mobile robots.

Results:

1. A CAD model of the rover was developed.
2. A prototype with Rocker-Bogie suspension was implemented.
3. A new navigation system, Local Pathing, was introduced.
4. Parts were modeled and analyzed using FEA and Generative Design, increasing structural stiffness more than eightfold.
5. A computer vision system for object detection and tracking was implemented.
6. The prototype successfully passed a series of tests.

Future Plans:

1. Integrate a hybrid localization system (LiDAR + camera) to improve accuracy.
2. Optimize computational algorithms for real-time performance.
3. Enhance the mechanical design using lightweight composite materials and more reliable mounts.
4. Expand the manipulator's capabilities to perform more complex tasks.
5. Develop a rover version for space missions (e.g., on Mars).

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

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A Local Pathing (LP) Algorithm Implementation

```
1 public class LPPathTracker {
2     // B zier curve control points
3     private final Coord2D cp0, cp1, cp2, cp3;
4     // PIDF controllers for linear and angular motion
5     private final FeedbackController linearController;
6     private final FeedbackController angularController;
7     // Maximum allowed centripetal acceleration
8     private final double curveAccelLimit;
9     // Current curve parameter
10    private double param = 0.0;
11
12    public LPPathTracker(Coord2D start, Coord2D ctrl1, Coord2D ctrl2,
13        Coord2D end, FeedbackController linearCtrl, FeedbackController
14        angularCtrl, double curveAccelLimit) {
15        this.cp0 = start;
16        this.cp1 = ctrl1;
17        this.cp2 = ctrl2;
18        this.cp3 = end;
19        this.linearController = linearCtrl;
20        this.angularController = angularCtrl;
21        this.curveAccelLimit = curveAccelLimit;
22    }
23
24    /** Compute point on B zier curve for parameter t */
25    private Coord2D computeBezier(double t) {
26        double u = 1 - t;
27        double b0 = u * u * u;
28        double b1 = 3 * u * u * t;
29        double b2 = 3 * u * t * t;
30        double b3 = t * t * t;
31        return
32        cp0.times(b0).plus(cp1.times(b1)).plus(cp2.times(b2)).plus(cp3.times(b3));
33    }
34
35    /** First derivative (tangent vector) */
36    private Coord2D computeFirstDerivative(double t) { ... }
37
38    /** Second derivative for curvature calculation */
39    private Coord2D computeSecondDerivative(double t) { ... }
40
41    /** Main update method called each control cycle */
42    public MotorOutput advance(Pose2D pose, double currentSpeed, double dt) {
43        // Estimate remaining distance along curve
44        double remaining = estimateRemainingDistance(param, 1.0);
45
46        // Compute desired speed via kinematic equation
47        double desiredDecel = -0.5;
48        double desiredSpeed = Math.sqrt(Math.max(0, -2 * desiredDecel * remaining));
49
50        // Account for natural deceleration (zero power decay)
51        double naturalAccel = -0.4;
52        double vf = Math.sqrt(Math.max(0, currentSpeed*currentSpeed + 2*naturalAccel*
53            remaining));
54        double decay = currentSpeed - vf;
55        desiredSpeed -= decay;
56
57        // Limit speed based on curvature
58        Coord2D d1 = computeFirstDerivative(param);
59        Coord2D d2 = computeSecondDerivative(param);
60        double curvature = Math.abs(d1.x*d2.y - d1.y*d2.x) / Math.pow(d1.x*d1.x + d1.y*
61            d1.y, 1.5);
62        double maxByCurve = curvature > 1e-6 ? Math.sqrt(curveAccelLimit / curvature) :
63            Double.POSITIVE_INFINITY;
64        double speedLimit = Math.min(desiredSpeed, maxByCurve);
65
66        // Linear PIDF control
67        double speedError = speedLimit - currentSpeed;
68        double linearOutput = linearController.update(speedError, dt) + linearController
69            .feedforward(speedLimit);
70    }
71 }
```

```

67     // Compute desired heading
68     Coord2D point = computeBezier(param);
69     Coord2D tangent = computeFirstDerivative(param).normalized();
70     double targetHeading = Math.atan2(tangent.y, tangent.x);
71     double headingError = normalizeAngle(targetHeading - pose.heading);
72     double angularOutput = angularController.update(headingError, dt);
73
74     // Convert to mecanum wheel speeds
75     double vx = linearOutput * Math.cos(pose.heading);
76     double vy = linearOutput * Math.sin(pose.heading);
77     return computeWheelSpeeds(vx, vy, angularOutput);
78 }
79 // Methods estimateRemainingDistance, normalizeAngle, computeWheelSpeeds implemented
80 // separately
}

```

B Vision-Based Object Tracking

```

1 public class VisionObjectTracker {
2     private final Scalar lowerHSV, upperHSV;
3     private final double focalPx, objectWidth;
4     private final PIDController distancePID, anglePID;
5     private final Mat kernel;
6
7     public VisionObjectTracker(Scalar lowerHSV, Scalar upperHSV,
8         double focalPx, double objectWidth,
9         PIDController distancePID,
10        PIDController anglePID) {
11        this.lowerHSV = lowerHSV;
12        this.upperHSV = upperHSV;
13        this.focalPx = focalPx;
14        this.objectWidth = objectWidth;
15        this.distancePID = distancePID;
16        this.anglePID = anglePID;
17        this.kernel = Imgproc.getStructuringElement(Imgproc.MORPH_RECT, new Size(5,5));
18    }
19
20    /** Process a frame and return wheel speeds */
21    public WheelSpeeds update(Mat frame, Pose2D currentPose, double dt) {
22        // Convert to HSV and threshold
23        Mat hsv = new Mat();
24        Imgproc.cvtColor(frame, hsv, Imgproc.COLOR_BGR2HSV);
25        Mat mask = new Mat();
26        Core.inRange(hsv, lowerHSV, upperHSV, mask);
27        Imgproc.erode(mask, mask, kernel);
28        Imgproc.dilate(mask, mask, kernel);
29
30        // Find contours
31        List<MatOfPoint> contours = new ArrayList<>();
32        Imgproc.findContours(mask, contours, new Mat(), Imgproc.RETR_EXTERNAL,
33            Imgproc.CHAIN_APPROX_SIMPLE);
34        if (contours.isEmpty()) return new WheelSpeeds(0,0,0,0);
35        MatOfPoint maxContour = Collections.max(contours,
36            Comparator.comparingDouble(Imgproc::contourArea));
37        Rect bbox = Imgproc.boundingRect(maxContour);
38
39        // Estimate distance and angle
40        double pixelWidth = bbox.width;
41        double centerX = bbox.x + bbox.width / 2.0;
42        double frameWidth = frame.cols();
43        double distance = (objectWidth * focalPx) / pixelWidth;
44        double angle = (centerX - frameWidth/2.0) * (fieldOfView / frameWidth);
45
46        // PID control
47        double linearError = targetDistance - distance;
48        double linearOut = distancePID.update(linearError, dt);
49        double angularOut = anglePID.update(-angle, dt);
50
51        // Convert to mecanum wheel speeds
52        double vx = linearOut * Math.cos(currentPose.heading);

```

```
53     double vy = linearOut * Math.sin(currentPose.heading);
54     return mecanumKinematics(vx, vy, angularOut);
55 }
56
57 private WheelSpeeds mecanumKinematics(double vx, double vy, double omega) {
58     double lf = vx - vy - omega;
59     double rf = vx + vy + omega;
60     double lb = vx + vy - omega;
61     double rb = vx - vy + omega;
62     return new WheelSpeeds(lf, rf, lb, rb);
63 }
64 }
```